

LTE NETWORK RADIO COVERAGE ASSESSMENT

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Annotatsiya. In the conditions of continuous growth of requirements for radio communication services at limitation of resources (frequencies, radio means and etc.) the most perspective direction of modernization and radio communication development is creation and introduction of complex digital system of the radio communication integrating all kinds of a railway radio communication (train, station, repair-operative, general technology, data transfer, etc.) and providing operational compatibility of available radio networks of all services [1-8]. An analysis of the capabilities of modern digital radio communication systems shows that their implementation, along with highly reliable radiotelephone (voice) communication, can provide a solution to many applied problems, including the organization of information transmission channels when creating a multi-level security system and train traffic control/

Keywords: LTE, Bandwidth, *The interference*, MIMO, QAM, the equivalent isotropic radiated transmitter power.

To evaluate the radio coverage, performance and capacity of the planned network, we will use the initial data:

- range – 2100 MHz;
- the allocated frequency band 20 MHz;
- frequency duplexing (FDD), in which the system frequency band is divided into 2 channels: 10 MHz for DL and 10 MHz for UL;
- modulation and coding scheme: 64QAM $\frac{1}{2}$ for DL and 16QAM $\frac{1}{2}$ for UL.

It is necessary to determine the maximum allowable losses on the line (MAL). They are calculated as the difference between the equivalent isotropic radiated transmitter power (EIRP) and the minimum required signal power at the input of the receiver of the conjugate side, at which normal signal demodulation in the receiver is ensured in the communication channel, taking into account all losses (fig. 1) [9, 10].

Figure 1. Determination of the maximum allowable losses on the line (MAL)

Consider a BS, the RF block of each sector, which is equipped with two transceivers, the output power of the transmitters is 20 W (43 dBm). The RF unit is installed in close proximity to the antenna. The base station operates on DL in MIMO 2x2 mode using a cross-polarization antenna. We calculate the energy budget for the UE at the edge of the cell, i.e. receiving signals from a BS with a low signal to noise ratio (SNR), in this regard, the BS transmits signals to the UE in the diversity transmission mode. By adding the powers of the signals of the two transmitters in space, you can get an energy gain (3 dB). As a UE, we consider a USB modem that has one transmitting and two receiving antennas (1x2 MIMO mode on UL), class 3 - EIRP 23 dBm.

The maximum allowable losses are calculated using the formula [10]:

$$L_{MAPL} = P_{EIRP} - S_{RX} + G_{RXA} - L_{RXF} - M_{BUILD} - M_{INT} - M_{SHADE} + G_{HO},$$

where P_{EIRP} – equivalent isotropic radiated transmitter power, dBm;

S_{RX} – receiver sensitivity, dBm;

G_{RXA} – the gain of the transmitter antenna, dBi;

L_{RXF} – losses in the feeder path of the receiver, dB;

M_{BUILD} – margin for signal penetration into the room, dB;

M_{INT} – margin for in-system interference, dB;

M_{SHADE} – stock up on the shading, dB;

G_{HO} , – the gain from the handover, dB.

EIRP for the transmitter is determined by the formula:

$$P_{EIRP} = P_{TX} + G_{TX,DIV} + G_{TX,A} - L_{TXF},$$

where P_{TX} – transmitter output power, dBm;

$G_{TX,DIV}$ – gain from adding up the power of transmitters, dB;

$G_{TX,A}$ – the gain of the transmitter antenna, dBi;

L_{TXF} – losses in the feeder path of the transmitter, dB.

The sensitivity of the receiver S_{RX} is determined by the formula:

$$S_{RX} = P_N + M_{SNR} + L_N,$$

where P_N – receiver thermal noise power, dBm;

M_{SNR} – required receiver signal-to-noise ratio, dB;

L_N , – the noise figure of the receiver, dB,

$$P_N = 10 \cdot \lg(1000 \cdot k \cdot T \cdot B),$$

where k – Boltzmann constant, $k = 1.38 \cdot 10^{-23}$;

T – absolute temperature, K ($T = 290$ K);

B – noise bandwidth of receiver:

$$B = N_{RB} \cdot \Delta f_k,$$

where N_{RB} – number of resource blocks allocated;

Δf_k – the frequency band of a single radio channel (a radio channel in LTE networks is defined as a resource block RB, which has a width of 180 kHz).

The value of the margin for in-system interference M_{INT} characterizes the increase in noise power at the receiver input. For the calculation assume that the margin for in system interference is equal to:

$$M_{INT} = -10 \lg(1 - \eta),$$

where η – relative load of a cell in an ascending or descending line.

The margin for in-system interference is a function of the cell load. the greater the permitted load in the cell, the greater the margin must be taken into account in the calculation. When the load increases to 100%, the margin for interference tends to infinity, and the service area of the cell is reduced to zero.

When calculating the MAL on the communication line, in addition to the characteristics of the transmitters and receivers, table 1 also took into account a number of other parameters and characteristics of the propagation medium, the physical meaning of which is described below.

The interference margin M_{Int} allows one to take into account the influence of interference from neighboring cells on the BS and MS, which is especially large for MS located at the cell boundaries. The M_{Int} value is in the range of 3... 8 dB [9].

Table 1

Characteristics of the LTE network communication channel

Line	DL	UL
<i>Transmitter</i>	<i>BS</i>	<i>MS</i>
Transmitter power output, P_{TX} , dBm	43	23
Number of Transmitters, M_{TX}	2	1

<i>Line</i>	<i>DL</i>	<i>UL</i>
Total transmitter power, $P_{TX\Sigma}$, dBm	46	23
The gain of the transmitting antenna, G_{ATX} , dBi	18	0
Losses in the feeder path of the transmitter, L_{FTX} , dBm	0,5	0
EIRP transmitter: $P_{EIRP} = P_{TX\Sigma} + G_{ATX} - L_{FTX}$, dBm	63,5	23
<i>Receiver</i>	<i>MC</i>	<i>BC</i>
The number of allocated resource blocks, N_{RB}	50	2
Receiver thermal noise power: $P_N = 10 \lg(1000kTB)$, dBm $k = 1,38 \cdot 10^{-23}$ – Boltzmann constant; $T = 290K$ – absolute temperature; $B = N_{RB} F_{RB}$ – receiver noise band; $F_{RB} = 180$ kHz – bandwidth of one resource block.	- 104,5	- 118,5
Receiver noise figure, N_F , dB	7	2
Signal to noise ratio and interference, S_{INR} , dB	- 1	1,5
Receiver sensitivity: $S_{RX} = P_N + N_F + S_{INR}$, dBm	- 98,5	- 115
The gain of the receiving antenna, G_{ARX} , dBi	0	18
Losses in the feeder path of the receiver, L_{FRX} , dB	0	0,5
Interference Reserve, M_{Int} , dB	8	3
Stock up on entering the room/car, M_{Build} , dB	17	17
Stock up on the shading, M_{Shade} , dB	8	8
The maximum allowable loss on line: $L_{MAPL} = P_{EIRP} - S_{RX} + G_{ARX} - L_{FRX} - M_{Int} - M_{Build} - M_{Shade}$, dB	129	127,5

The penetration margin of an M_{Build} must be taken into account due to the different signal attenuation depending on the terrain class. For the 2600 MHz band, the following penetration margin values can be used: 22 dB - in dense urban areas; 17 dB - in the conditions of medium urban development; 12 dB - in conditions of rare development and in the suburbs; 8 dB - in the countryside, in the park and in the car in the open [10].

The shading margin of M_{Shade} takes into account the attenuation of the signal due to the movement of the MS, since this often leads to a loss of line of sight between the MS and the BS. Standard value $M_{Shade} = 8$ dB [11].

Graphs Dependence of the distance between the receiver and the transmitter (d) on the installation height of the transmitter antenna h_B at different heights of the

receiver antenna h_M at frequencies of 900 MHz and 2100 MHz for DL and UL are given below (fig. 2-5).

Figure 2. Dependence of the distance between the receiver and the transmitter (d) on the installation height of the transmitter antenna h_B at various heights of the receiver antenna h_M at a frequency of 900 MHz for DL

Figure 3. Dependence of the distance between the receiver and the transmitter (d) on the installation height of the transmitter antenna h_B at different heights of the receiver antenna h_M at a frequency of 900 MHz for UL

Figure 4. Dependence of the distance between the receiver and the transmitter (d) on the installation height of the transmitter antenna h_B at various heights of the receiver antenna h_M at a frequency of 2100 MHz for DL

Figure 5. Dependence of the distance between the receiver and the transmitter (d) on the installation height of the transmitter antenna h_B at various heights of the receiver antenna h_M at a frequency of 2100 MHz for UL

CONCLUSION

The analysis showed that the distance between the receiver and the transmitter (d) from the installation height of the transmitter antenna h_B at different heights of the receiver antenna h_M for UL and UL is relatively different from each other. Therefore, when designing a digital radio communication standard, it is necessary to be guided by the minimum value for determining the cell radius.

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